

Analysing the congestion impact of deliveries schedule observation in urban construction sites

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Keywords: urban logistics, construction logistics, case study, delivery scheduling

Abstract: In the context of urban construction logistics, this paper analyses the usage of delivery schedules, their observation and their impact on congestion. Logistics data were collected during 8 months on 4 construction sites in 4 European cities. Using qualitative and quantitative analyses, the authors expose the specificities of construction logistics and its impact in urban areas, in particular the impact of delivery time window scheduling on roads and site congestion. In conclusion, the authors propose solution leads that will be further explored in the framework of a European project, among others the use of Construction Consolidation Centres in urban areas.

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1. Introduction

This paper relates the findings of a data analytics study performed in the context of the European Sustainable Urban Consolidation Centres for construction (SUCCESS) project. The project aims to improve the efficiency and reduce negative impacts of the construction supply chain by exploring and testing reliable and innovative solutions. The SUCCESS project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 633338.

Part of a larger analysis of the construction logistics, this study focuses on analysing the respect of deliveries schedules, their causes and their impact in the context of construction sites' urban logistics. In section two, we expose the three main research questions which have guided the study. In sections three and four, we describe the state of the art on urban logistics and deliveries scheduling as well as the specific context of construction logistics in general and in urban area. Last we describe the context of the SUCCESS research project and its four pilots' sites. Section five describes the research method based on pilot sites data collection, the assumptions and data relationship underlying the analysis, and the building of an analytic grid using the root causes analysis technique. Section six describes the findings of the quantitative analysis and section seven concludes the paper with the main findings.

In today's competitive business environment, customers require their suppliers to be dependable in delivering on-time shipments making the improvement of the delivery performance one of the goals of supply chain management. The delivery reliability is a key concern to customers and many empirical studies have documented the importance that on-time delivery plays in the operation of the supply chain (Bushuev and Guiffrida, 2012).

In its Strategic Research Agenda for 2030 (Smit et al., 2010) and later in its Urban Freight Roadmap (ALICE (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe), 2015), ERTRAC (European Road Transport Research Advisory Council) confirms the importance of improving the reliability of transport schedule and ranks it as a leading indicator. The guiding objective is to achieve, by 2030, a 50 per cent increase in the reliability of transport schedules versus 2010 baseline. This indicator involves all modes and is strongly linked to economic growth and aims at reducing congestion and the significant societal costs. Improvements in this indicator will require the optimization of the entire urban mobility system, with regard to economic and societal challenges.

In many studies, the delivery reliability and performance are analysed from the carrier point of view. Taniguchi proposed several quantitative methods based on vehicle routing problem analyses to evaluate the impact of time constraints and delivery performance for city logistics (Taniguchi et al., 1999; Taniguchi and Kakimoto, 2004; Taniguchi and Thompson, 2002). If we consider the delivery operations from a receiver perspective, delivery conditions and time constraints have a different impact depending on the sector (Marcucci et al., 2014).

Freight carriers transporting and delivering goods to industries benefit from a good facilities. Located outside the cities, industries benefit from a good access to the transport network and enough space to store large volume and propose turning area. They receive the goods directly from platforms making easier and faster the deliveries (*BESTUFS Good Practice Guide*, 2009). In busy urban areas, the cities need to provide dedicated space for deliveries operations in location that generate goods vehicle trips such as business districts and retail areas to improve working conditions for transport operators and also address the negative impacts that can be caused by delivery operations. Although transport operators struggle to find available space, they still can park. Since businesses are supplied on just-in-time and have minimal storage space for deliveries, the urban freight distribution generates high frequency deliveries and smaller volumes (Rodrigue and Dablanc, 2017). They use mainly vans and trucks. Vans up to 3.5 tons in weight tend to be more adapted and popular to deliver in urban areas (Browne et al., 2010). Semi-trailers and trucks with a trailer are also used in lower volumes. They are mainly used for supermarkets which benefits from their own loading facilities. The delivery operations are relatively short. In Paris, the delivery lasts on average 10 minutes in the city centre (Patier, 2011).

Night / off-hours delivery is a city logistics initiative allowing normal activity during the day and availability of goods in the early morning. The solution is implemented in many cities around the world (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). By allowing larger trucks to deliver off-peak, the travel time is reduced and the delivery is more efficient in resources consumptions and pollutant emissions. We can distinguish two types of night delivery: Staffed Off-Hours Delivery (SOHD), that imply additional staff engagement for the reception and thus additional cost of labour in addition to night work and Unassisted Off-Hours Delivery (UOHD), with no staff for assistance when accepting the goods which is less expensive but also less safe.

When it comes to deliver construction sites, the delivery exercise is even more difficult. Firstly, the off-street loading areas usually don't exist or don't fit the deliveries operations. Because of the nature of the goods, the transport operators have to deliver as close as possible. It implies the receiver, the construction company, to create off-street loading areas inside the site or on-

street loading areas along the fence on a space that the receiver rents to the city. The loading areas on a construction site are temporary and its number varies along the planning. Secondly, the space available on the site varies between projects and varies according to the progress of the construction within each project. The same applies for the number of goods delivered to the site. Finally, most of the transport operators rely on the handling equipment of the construction site which are shared between the construction activities. On a construction site, the most critical handling equipment is the crane. The construction sector is more constrained by the scarce space for deliveries and temporary storage of materials. Traditionally, deliveries arrive on construction sites throughout the day, convenient to the supplier delivery routing. Since the Just-In-Time philosophy advocates the elimination of non-value adding activities, deliveries in a lean approach arrive on construction sites within a scheduled delivery slot, convenient to the construction operation and in line with their build plan (Lundesjö, 2015). The literature review shows the specificities of deliveries to construction sites in urban areas (Allen et al., 2014; Browne et al., 2005; Ville et al., 2010). Some construction companies plan their deliveries on a fixed delivery time, others within a delivery window and last ones use both approaches. Guiffrida (Bushuev and Guiffrida, 2012) defines a delivery window as the difference between the earliest acceptable delivery date and the latest acceptable delivery date. Within a delivery window, a delivery can be classified as being early, on-time, or late. Early and late deliveries introduce waste in the form of excess waste in the supply chain; early deliveries contribute to excess inventory holding costs while late deliveries may contribute to production stoppage costs, lost sales and loss of goodwill. These costs have been characterised as penalty costs. So far, it seems that no study compares the two types of delivery scheduling. For this reason, we aim to propose in this paper a deep analysis of the differences between the two types of delivery scheduling and their impact on the congestion inside and outside the site.

2. Context of the construction sites logistics in urban area

The construction industry is often compared to other sectors such as manufacturing. Still, progress in applying traditional supply chain management practices from those sectors to the construction industry is difficult. According to Koskela (Koskela, 1992), the construction is unique in the sense of it is one-of kind nature of projects, site production and temporary multi-organization.

The high fragmentation of the sector involves a wide variety of stakeholders (architects, contractors, owners...) with different interests. The main contractor coordinates the various

stakeholders (often but not always their sub-contractors) on the construction site and his main challenge is to schedule stakeholders' interventions. The main contractor has a limited vision of the supply chain due to this wide variety of actors: each sub-contractor is responsible for ordering materials needed but cannot schedule the deliveries on site independently. Thus the stakeholders have to synchronise with the main contractor for scheduling their material deliveries on the site. Whereas in traditional retail or industry sectors, shippers tend outsource transport services to a third party, shippers in construction (mainly material suppliers) rely mainly on own-account transport. The consequences include an increase in pollution, congestion, noise, accidents and poor level of transport activities. Considering that building materials can make up to 30% of tons carried in cities, the construction represents a key urban freight segment because of the important tonnage they generate (Dablanc, 2009).

In the first phase of the SUCCESS project, 4 different types of construction sites (residential, commercial, offices, specific activity) with different sizes (1 small site < 30 000 m², 2 medium sites < 50 000 m² and 1 big site > 100 000 m²) in different types of urban area (middle density urban area close to a motorway exit, dense urban area of a metropolis so not easily accessible, dense urban area of a major city, but still remains easily accessible from motorways, dense residential area, close the old city center of a mid-size city) were observed daily over 8 months representing the records of 4436 deliveries and pickups trips.

Deliveries related to a limited set of materials and are not necessary representative of all materials required on the construction site. In addition each construction site had its own and independent construction planning so not all sites were observed in the same phase of the construction project.

This study is based on multiple questions at the cross-road of urban logistics and logistics of construction sites.

The first research question that drove the study is

RQ1: How delivery schedules are used by urban construction sites?

With this question we aim at determining whether deliveries and pickups in the construction sector are scheduled and under which form. This research question can then be further declined in two sub-questions:

- a. In which context and in which proportion delivery schedule are used in the construction sector?
- b. What kinds of delivery schedules are used?

Answering this first question raises a second one:

RQ2: How delivery schedules are observed in the urban construction logistics?

To answer this question we need to characterise the context and the specificities of urban construction sites and construction logistics. Then we can address the question in the light of this context, which will lead to a third and final question:

RQ3: What are the impacts of observing/missing delivery schedule in construction urban logistics and their specificities due to the construction sector?

We can answer this question by first determining the causes of schedule inobservance and then by analysing the internal and external impacts of such inobservance in the relationship with the causes.

3. Research method

In order to answer the above questions we applied the following methodology. First we identified a set of KPI to monitor logistics activities on urban construction sites. Then we designed the data collection principles and templates that were disseminated on each site. We performed a root cause analysis to identify the different delivery schedule cases. Next each construction site designated a person in charge of collecting data daily on their own site over the data collection period. Last at the end of the data collection period, we performed a quantitative analysis on the collected data, using the results of the root causes analysis as an additional analytical framework. We eventually checked the validity of some assumptions and results with a correlation analysis.

3.1. Observations and data collection

In the SUCCESS project, one of the first activity was the identification of Key Performance Indicators to measure urban construction logistics, in parallel with the design of data sets and data collection methods to measure these KPIs as summarised in Table 1. It is worth to note that several data were collected for the purpose of the SUCCESS project, while this paper only focuses on a limited subset of those data (as highlighted in table 1). The data were collected daily by direct observation of dedicated workers on construction sites then reported in spreadsheets and loaded in specific databases where quality controls were performed to ensure consistency and confidence in the data collection.

Table 1: Data collected for KPI computation (excerpt). Highlighted data are part of the analysis reported in this paper.

Key Performance Indicator

		CO ₂ equivalent emissions	Congestion on construction site	Construction site punctuality	Distance from the production to the construction site	Loading / unloading time	Particulate Matter emissions	Travel time inside the city centre	Travel time outside the city centre	Truck punctuality	Truck waiting time inside the site	Truck waiting time outside the site
Data collected on construction site	Address of the loading location				X							
	Address of the previous delivery 2				X							
	Address of the previous delivery 1				X							
	Address of next delivery 1				X							
	Address of next delivery 2				X							
	Address of final come back				X							
	Starting time from the loading location (time)								X			
	Arrival time in urban area (time)							X	X			
	Arrival time near the construction site (time)							X		X		X
	Planned delivery time 1 (time)			X						X		
	Planned delivery time 2 (time)			X						X		
	Arrival time at construction site (time)		X								X	X
	Starting time of unloading (time)			X		X					X	
	Ending time of unloading (time)		X			X						
	Material weight (kg)	X					X					
	Roundtrip or Direct trip (choice list)				X							
	Come back empty or loaded (choice list)	X			X		X					
	Vehicle Euroclass (choice list)	X					X					
	Vehicle Fuel type (choice list)	X					X					
	Gross vehicle weight rating (GVWR) (kg)	X					X					
	Vehicle Net weight (kg)	X					X					
	Vehicle surface (sqm)		X									
Vehicle type (choice list)	X					X						

In the context of this paper, we only focus on trips' time-related data that were collected among pilots' deliveries and pickups. Basically for a delivery trip, data were collected about: the trip **starting** time, the trip time of arrival **near** the construction site meaning that the trucks is nearby the construction site without having yet entered the site, the trip time of arrival **at** the

construction site meaning the time at which the trucks effectively enters in the construction site, the **starting time of unloading** and the **ending time of unloading**. Figure 1 represents the usual sequence of time records collected on each observation.

When a delivery or a pickup trip was scheduled, in case of a fixed time schedule, the **scheduled time** of truck arrival **at** the site was recorded or, in case of a scheduled time window, the **schedule time interval** during which the truck is expected to arrive **at** the site. When the delivery is not scheduled, no scheduled time nor interval is recorded.

3.2. Underlying assumptions

The following assumptions, which will be further used for the root cause analysis, are formalised on the basis of the observations of the data collectors on the construction sites.

From start to near time, we do not make any distinction on whether the trip is a round trip or a direct trip. When the truck arrives near the site, we assume that the truck driver stops the truck in the surrounding area and waits until he can enter into the construction site. The decision to allow a truck to enter into the construction site is taken by the construction site (not by the truck driver). When entered in the site, we assume that the driver drives the truck to the unloading location, eventually with intermediate stops inside the construction site (e.g. if the truck is queued before being unloaded) and waits until the unloading starts. Last as soon as the unloading ends, we assume that the driver drives the truck out of the construction site immediately.

3.3. Relationships between data collected.

Based on the assumptions one can infer various information on trip from data combinations.

First, information on trip's activities durations (what is the truck doing and how long?): **travelling** duration is inferred from the difference between **start** and **near**, **waiting** duration is inferred from the difference between **near** and **unloading start**; **unloading** duration is inferred from the difference between **unloading start** and **unloading end**.

Next, information on truck duration at a specific “place” (where is the truck and how long?): the truck is **outside the construction** site before the “at” time point and **inside the construction site** after the “at’ time point.

Then information on truck and site punctuality can only be measured in the case of scheduled trips. The **truck punctuality** is measured by comparing the scheduled time of arrival and the truck arrival time near the construction site. When the near time point precedes the schedule time point the truck is ahead of schedule, when both time points coincide the truck is on time and when the near time point follows the schedule time point the truck is behind schedule. In case of scheduled time window the arrival time is compared to either to the lower bound of the interval for truck ahead of schedule or to the upper bound for truck behind schedule. When the schedule interval overlaps the time point, the truck is on time.

The same reasoning applies for **construction site punctuality** by comparing the scheduled time of arrival and the truck arrival time at the construction site. When the “at” time point precedes the schedule time point (or the lower bound of the schedule interval) the construction site is ahead of schedule, when both time points coincide (or when the time point overlaps the schedule interval) the construction site is on time and when the “at” time point follows the schedule time point (or the upper bound of the schedule interval) construction site is behind schedule.

3.4. Root causes analysis

We used an approach based on the thinking process (Dettmer, 2007) to analyse the root causes of truck waiting in case of scheduled trip and thus the cause of congestion due to truck waiting. We also identified the location where the truck is waiting (on the roads outside the site or inside the site) in combination with the cause of the truck waiting, to characterise both impact and cause of congestion due to truck waiting. With this root cause analysis we identified the different delivery schedule cases and sub cases (Table 2).

Table 2: summary of delivery cases after the root cause analysis

		Site punctuality		
		ahead of schedule	on schedule	behind schedule
Truck punctuality	ahead of schedule	1.a 1.b	1.c	1.d
	on schedule		2.a	2.b
	behind schedule			3.a 3.b

In the first case (1) the truck is ahead of schedule. In the best case (1.a) the truck ahead of schedule does not wait at all. In a second sub-case (1.b) the truck ahead of schedule does wait but is still unloaded earlier than scheduled: the cause of the truck waiting time is due to the early arrival.

Figure 2 Illustration of case 1 and sub cases

If the truck arrives ahead of schedule and is unloaded at the scheduled time (1.c) we still have to breakdown into further sub-cases depending on the type of schedule. When the schedule is a fixed time (1.c.1), then the cause of the truck waiting is totally due to its early arrival. When the schedule is a time window (1.c.2), the cause of the truck waiting is partly due to its early arrival and partly due to the time window schedule. Depending on whether the truck enters the site before the lower bound of the time window (1.c.2.a) or after the lower bound (1.c.2.b), the combination of truck waiting cause and truck waiting location changes. When the construction site is behind the schedule while the truck is still ahead of schedule (1.d), then the causes of the truck waiting time are the truck early arrival, the delay of the construction site and possibly the time window schedule. We need additional break down to deeper analyse the impact of each of these three causes on road congestion and site congestion, depending on whether the trucks enter the construction site before the time window (1.d.1), within the time window (1.d.2) or after the time window (1.d.3).

In a second case the truck is on schedule. In the best sub-case (2.a) both truck and construction site are on schedule. The truck does not wait if both truck and construction site are on schedule on a fixed time schedule (2.a.1), but the truck can wait in case of time window schedule (2.a.2) and the cause is the time window schedule. When the truck is on schedule and the construction site is behind schedule (2.b), this generates a truck waiting time. In case of fixed time schedule (2.b.1) the cause of the waiting time is the delay of the construction site. In case of a time window schedule (2.b.2), when the truck enters the site during the time window (2.b.2.a), the road congestion is fully due to time window scheduling, while the site congestion is partly due

to time window scheduling and site delay. When the truck enters the site after the time window (2.b.2.b), the road congestion is partly due to time window scheduling and site delay, while the site congestion is fully due to site delay.

Figure 3 Illustration of sub-cases under case 2

In the last main case (3) the truck is behind schedule and consequently is the construction site. In the best case (3.a), despite the delay, the construction site can handle the truck immediately at its arrival. In the worst case (3.b), the construction site is not available to handle the truck at its late arrival and the truck has to wait for the site availability.

Figure 4 Illustration of sub-cases under case 3

4. As-Is analysis

We used the cases analytic grid detailed on the preceding section on the data collected by the pilots' construction sites in order to analyse quantitatively the causes and impact of congestion. The results are represented in Figure 5. Out of the 4 pilot construction sites, one site extensively used deliveries scheduling (less than 13% of deliveries were scheduled), while the three others sites did intensively used scheduled delivery (between 45% and 98% of deliveries were scheduled). For this specific site where scheduled deliveries are almost not used (Site 4) the scheduled deliveries were not representative enough from the site deliveries, so we did not consider this particular site in the analysis.

In the three remaining sites, one site (Site 2) uses only fixed time delivery schedule while the two other sites use only (Site 3) or mainly (Site 1) time window schedule. For Site 1 time window schedule is used in majority (65% of scheduled deliveries) while fixed time delivery schedule is used in minor case (35% of scheduled deliveries).

Due to the very specific situation of each site (different cities, different countries, different type of construction, different organisations...) we do not intend to compare the sites among each other, but rather identify generic trends.

On the **comparison between site and road congestions** for each site, one can first note the absence site congestion on site 2. This is due to the logistics policy of the dedicated logistics team on the site that is organised so that a truck has no down-time as soon as it enter the site. This organisation is efficient in this goal, but this does not prevent the congestion on roads nearby the site and may eventually report the congestion outside the site. For the two other sites, the congestion on site is at the level or above the congestion on roads nearby. For Site 3 the congestion is much higher on site than on road, but this can be explained by the large capacity

of the site that allows trucks to wait inside rather than outside. On a tighter site like Site 1, roads and site congestions are more balanced.

On the **time window scheduling impact on congestion**, one notes clearly that time window scheduling generates truck waiting, and then congestion both on site and on roads. For the two sites concerned, time window scheduling is the first cause of congestion both on road and on site, but one note a higher impact (larger difference with other congestion causes) on site than on road. As we do not have collected the information on which part (haulier vs. construction site) has requested and determined the delivery time window, one cannot draw explicit conclusions on that finding. In our analysis, we found almost no correlation between the size of the time window and the duration of the truck waiting due to the time window (see Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation analysis between size of the time window schedule and truck waiting time due to time window

Site	Impact	r ²	p-value
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Site 1	Road congestion	-0.06	4.58e-01
Site 1	Site congestion	0.02	7.96e-01
Site 3	Site congestion	0.33	6.21e-19
Site 3	Road congestion	0.07	8.57e-02

On the **impacts of other causes on congestion**, conclusions are more difficult to draw since they seem specific to the context of each site and cannot be generalised. Confirming natural perception, truck early arrival impacts more road congestion than site congestion, since construction sites are not eager to allow early truck to enter their site with the risk to disturb their planning. On the other side, site lateness impacts more site congestion than road congestion since sites are more willing to compensate their own lateness by welcoming the trucks on their site rather than congesting the roads nearby.

5. Conclusions

Construction logistics is a specialised form of logistics due to the specific context of construction with regard to other business sectors (retail or manufacturing among others). According to the PMBoK and Prince2 methodologies which are the main project management methodologies (OGC, 2009; Project Management Institute, 2013), construction sites are by nature projects since they are non-permanent structures in time and location, which forces hauliers and constructions companies to adapt differently at every new construction. In urban logistics, construction logistics is even more specific. Indeed, while retails and services located in urban area can usually adapt their deliveries to the urban context (smaller trucks, more frequent deliveries), construction sites have much more difficulties to do so due to the nature, size and volumes of their deliveries. In addition, construction sites have a wide range of organisation and of maturity level with regards to logistics management and project management, which results in various levels of efficiency in urban logistics.

From a general point of view, our study shows that analysing the compliance of deliveries or pickup schedules can lead to determine the causes of truck waiting and thus the causes of congestions. Congestion can be a haulier cause (early arrival), a consignee cause (site delay) or can be shared (time window schedule, truck delay and site unavailability).

Our empirical conclusions rely on the quantitative analysis of only 4 construction sites. Although the sites are quite diverse in size, type of construction, size of cities and location within the cities, the generalisation of our conclusions would need additional analysis for further

validation. The main conclusions on the analysis of the congestion causes due to truck waiting are focused on two main points:

- First the fact of scheduling deliveries with a time window can, in certain cases, generate congestion specifically due the fact that the schedule is a time interval. Within this interval both haulier and site can be “on schedule” while the truck is still waiting, thus generating congestion. From our observations, this congestion occurs mainly on site and in a lower extent on roads nearby.
- Second as analysed on one site, the fact of trying not to congest the construction site, which could be seen as a good practice in the scope of the site’s logistics, may report part of the congestion on the roads nearby and then is more mitigated with regards to the global logistics efficiency of the site and its surroundings.

As generic improvement recommendations one can suggest to carefully consider the congestion impact when using time window delivery scheduling. Although no clear evidence has been found of the impact of the time window size on the congestion due to truck waiting but because in certain cases it can generate truck waiting which cause is directly the fact of scheduling in a time window, time window should be as small as possible.

The SUCCESS project will think beyond local construction logistics optimisation, by exploring more global solutions such as Construction Consolidation Centre (CCC). In particular SUCCESS will provide simulations of optimisations without or with CCC. The use of a CCC can smooth the delivery process by having a dedicated and highly available logistics team and then limit the truck waiting in urban areas and construction sites. Indeed a CCC could avoid scheduling its inbound deliveries and could manage the scheduling of outbound deliveries to the construction sites in closer relationship than the usual suppliers, thus reducing the waiting time of truck in or nearby the site and the CCC. Even a storage buffer zone close or adjacent to the construction site and used as a CCC annex in between the CCC and the construction site, could be used to absorb congestion and deliver the construction site just in time. The truck would no longer wait on the site, but rather in this buffer zone, reducing congestion on site and on street. Eventually, night or off-peak deliveries seem more complex to set up for construction sites, since sites’ handling equipment are usually requested for unloading deliveries and since unassisted deliveries does not seem feasible in practice for construction materials. Last, the use of BIM (Building Information Modeling) in construction project management is an opportunity to collect data on all components of the building to be constructed (Rokooei, 2015). Such database could help to have a forward view on the materials to be delivered on the construction site. Based on this list of materials, it can be easier for the construction company to organise

the logistic flows of its site to master its supplies and then to have a better organisation of the delivery scheduling. The digital transformation of the construction sector will bring data to stakeholders to improve the construction supply chains.

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